

Arctic Deep Seabed Mining in Norway: Government Policies vs Public Opinion

Alexandra Middleton*

Introduction

The green transition to reduce carbon emissions and provide sustainable energy requires an unprecedented increase in the supply of critical metals such as lithium, cobalt, and rare earth elements.¹ These metals are crucial for technologies that range from electric vehicles, wind turbines, and solar panels. Some of the arguments for deep seabed mining include the depletion of land mineral repositories and dependence on the Chinese supply of these critical minerals²; hence, deep-sea mining is gaining traction as a potential solution to supplement growing demand. According to World Bank forecasts, 500% more production of these minerals is expected in 2050 to meet the surge in clean energy technologies.³

As part of the momentum to meet green transition needs, Norway approved an expedited exploration of the Arctic deep

seabed for minerals on January 9, 2024. The approval opens up to exploration of about 280,000 sq. km of the Arctic seabed, an area bigger than the United Kingdom. The area is in the Barents Sea and Greenland Sea, west of the Arctic islands that make up the Svalbard archipelago.⁴ This deep seabed area is estimated to have rich deposits of sulphides and manganese crusts containing valuable minerals such as copper, zinc, cobalt, and rare earth elements.⁵

Norway's decision to open the deep seabed for exploration has become highly controversial.

* Postdoctoral Researcher, Fulbright Arctic Initiative Scholar 2024-2026, University of Oulu.

¹ Vysetti, B. (2023). Deep-sea mineral deposits as a future source of critical metals, and environmental issues—A brief review. *Miner. Miner. Mater.*, 2(5).

² Xia, Q., Du, D., Yu, Z., Li, X., & Zhang, Q. (2024). Coins have both sides: Revealing the structure and pattern of global interdependence network for five critical metals. *Resources Policy*, 88, 104453.

³ Vatalis, K. I., Platias, S., & Charalampides, G. (2021). Planning Sustainable Deep Sea Mining. *Materials Proceedings*, 5(1), 9.

⁴ Jamasmie, C. (2024). Norway approves deep sea mining in Arctic Ocean. *Mining.com*. <https://www.mining.com/norway-approves-deep-sea-mining-in-arctic-ocean/>

⁵ Kjørstad, E. (2024). Here's how valuable resources can be extracted from the seabed: "There's a goldmine out there". <https://www.sciencenorway.no/deep-sea-mineralogy-mining/heres-how-valuable-resources-can-be-extracted-from-the-seabed-theres-a-goldmine-out-there/2285672>

Norway's decision to open the deep seabed for exploration has become highly controversial. Critics note that the environmental risks and possible damage to deep-ocean ecosystems outweigh the economic benefits. On the global scale environmental organizations, scientists, and some governments opposed Norway's decision.^{6,7} Domestically, the decision polarized public opinion, as proponents believe it could boost economic growth and resource security while opponents raised concerns about the environmental and ethical implications.

In this article, I discuss the rationale of this decision as presented by the Norwegian government and domestic public views analyzed from the media discourse and open public consultation documents. Furthermore, I elaborate on the legal challenges associated with this decision.

Historical Analysis of Norway's Deep-Sea Bed Mining Initiative

The Norwegian government-initiated discussions on the prospects of deep-seabed mining in 2020.⁸ This initial proposal set the stage for research and environmental assessments, leading to approval for exploration in January 2024.

In 2020, the Government of Norway proposed deep-seabed mining as a potential new industry. The first proposal regarding the initiation of mineral extraction from the seabed was motivated by the rising demand for minerals, which was becoming crucial for green technologies.⁹ This led to the initiation of research and environmental assessment to understand the impacts and benefits of deep-sea mining, which marked the beginning of a coordinated research effort to compile scientific information and stakeholder interests. During 2021–2022, the focus was on conducting environmental studies and resource mapping. These studies aimed to identify the locations and quantities of valuable minerals, such as copper, zinc, cobalt, and rare earth elements, on the Arctic seabed.

⁶ Norway's approval of sea-bed mining undermines efforts to protect the ocean. (2024). *Nature*, 625(7995), 424–424. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-00104-w>

⁷ Bjørnstad, L. (2024). Norway strongly criticised in Nature editorial for approving seabed mining. <https://www.sciencenorway.no/business-climate-policy-mineralogy/norway-strongly-criticised-in-nature-editorial-for-approving-seabed-mining/2317159>

⁸ Perl, A. (2024). Mining the depths: Norway's deep-sea exploitation could put it in environmental and legal murky waters. <https://theconversation.com/mining-the-depths-norways-deep-sea-exploitation-could-put-it-in-environmental-and-legal-murky-waters-220909>

⁹ European Parliament (2024). Norway to mine part of the Arctic seabed. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2024/757616/EPRS_ATA%282024%29757616_EN.pdf

The government collaborated with scientific institutions to ensure an understanding of the environmental conditions and potential impacts of mining activities.¹⁰

In June 2023, the Norwegian government proposed the opening of 281,000 square kilometers of the Arctic deep seabed for exploration. According to critics, the environmental impact assessment accompanying the proposal was not sufficiently detailed. Environmental groups and scientists claimed that the assessment did not adequately address potential ecological impacts and thus called for larger studies.¹¹ This stage signalled a rising conflict between economic interests and environmental concerns.

Following this proposal, public consultations were held in July 2023. Various stakeholders, including environmental groups, scientists, and local

communities, were invited to voice their opinions and concerns. These consultations revealed significant opposition to the proposal, with many arguing that the environmental risks were too high and that more detailed studies were needed.^{12,13} The feedback from these consultations played a crucial role in shaping the subsequent parliamentary review. In September 2023, the Norwegian Parliament reviewed the proposal. The opposition parties and environmentalists continued to object that the environmental impact assessments were insufficient and insisted on more detailed studies, considering the ecological destruction that may have been caused.¹⁴ The government underscored the economic interest and strategic value of securing supplies of minerals crucial for green technologies.

The Norwegian Parliament approved the exploration of minerals in

¹⁰ Eco-Safe Ridge Mining: Environmental risk studies towards sustainable seabed mineral mining on the Mid-Ocean Ridge in Norway. NORCE (2024). <https://www.norceresearch.no/en/projects/eco-safe-ridge-mining>

¹¹ Albert, E.C. (2024). 'Really a sad day' as Norway votes to allow deep-sea mining in Arctic waters. <https://news.mongabay.com/2024/01/really-a-sad-day-as-norway-votes-to-allow-deep-sea-mining-in-arctic-waters/>

¹² Norway's proposal to move forward with commercial deep-sea mining must be rejected. Environmental Justice (2023). <https://ejfoundation.org/news-media/norways-decision-to-move-forward-with-commercial-deep-sea-mining-must-be-opposed-to-avoid-irrevocable-damage>

¹³ Albert, E.C. (2024). Norway poised to sail past opposition with deep-sea mining licensing plans. <https://news.mongabay.com/2024/10/norway-poised-to-sail-past-opposition-with-deep-sea-mining-licensing-plans/>

¹⁴ Norway's approval of Arctic deep seabed mining could collide with international law. WWF (2023). <https://www.arcticwwf.org/newsroom/features/norways-approval-of-arctic-deep-seabed-mining-could-collide-with-international-law/>

the Arctic seabed on January 9, 2024.¹⁵ The decision allowed the activities of exploration to begin, although actual mining licenses are only to be approved later by the Parliament and are not believed to be issued until the early 2030s. Approval constitutes the latest milestone in the deep-sea bed mining initiative of Norway, despite some opposition and demands for more stringent environmental protection. In turn, public opposition by environmental groups and political parties called for a more detailed environmental impact assessment.

The Norwegian government rationalizes its approach to deep-sea bed exploration by framing it as part of a larger resource strategy. Astrid Bergmål, State Secretary in the Norwegian Ministry of Petroleum and Energy noted: "*The reason for us to look into seabed minerals is the large amount of critical minerals that will be needed for many years.*"¹⁶ The Norwegian Government portrays the view of careful progression; for example, Terje Aasland, Norway's Minister for Petroleum and Energy, highlighted this by stating, "*We*

will do this carefully, we will do it step by step. We will collect knowledge, then we will assess whether it is possible to start with this extraction."¹⁷ Marianne Sivertsen Næss, Chair of The Standing Committee on Energy and the Environment, echoed this sentiment by stressing the current knowledge gap. Næss explained, "*We do not currently have the knowledge needed to extract minerals from the seabed in the manner required.*" Næss further clarified that the government's proposal is aimed at enabling private actors to explore and gather data without equating the opening of areas to automatic approval of extraction.¹⁸

While the Norwegian government framed deep-seabed exploration as a strategic move in securing critical minerals, the approach raised concerns among critics. Critics argue that this assurance of a cautious, knowledge-driven process from the government is not convincing, given the large gaps in existing knowledge and potential environmental risks.

¹⁵ Norway gives green light for seabed minerals. The Norwegian Government (2024).

<https://www.regjeringen.no/en/aktuelt/norway-gives-green-light-for-seabed-minerals/id3021433/>

¹⁶ Videmšek, B. (2024). Cold War at the Bottom of the Sea. <https://revolve.media/features/deep-sea-mining-norway>

¹⁷ Deep-sea mining in the Arctic Ocean gets the green light from Norwegian lawmakers. APnews (2024). <https://apnews.com/article/norway-underwater-mining-arctic-663c7fceba5fc41e84affc5f84d52504>

¹⁸ Stallard, E. (2024). Deep-sea mining: Norway approves controversial practice. <https://www.bbc.com/news/science-environment-67893808>

Opposition voices and public opinion

The approval of the exploration of minerals in the Arctic deep seabed by the Norwegian Government was met with strong opposition by opposition parties, as well as environmental organizations such as the WWF, who had pointed out environmental and legal issues as reasons for not opening these areas. The chief executive of WWF-Norway, Karoline Andaur, described the move as “*an unprecedented management scandal.*” According to Andaur, the government was “*arrogantly setting aside scientific advice in defiance of the warnings of the marine research community.*” The decision has serious implications for the risk of severe damage to marine ecosystems and is in contravention of the principles of responsible management of resources.¹⁹

In April 2024, WWF-Norway further stepped up its objection when it declared that it would take the Norwegian government to court for failure to meet requirements on impact assessments under the Seabed Minerals Act. Andaur then lamented that the mere threat of a lawsuit did not deter the government from its course: “*WWF-Norway sees no other*

options but to proceed with legal action.”²⁰ Andaur also said that the actions of the government broke Norwegian law since they opened the door to an industry that was potentially destructive without considering all the consequences. Andaur believes that allowing this would be a dangerous precedent because it would weaken the protection of the environment and resource management.

Kaja Loenne Fjaertoft, Global Policy Lead at WWF, added that the licensing process was rushed, with insufficient attention paid to environmental authorities’ advice. Similarly, opposition parties have criticized the lack of detailed environmental impact assessments, calling for more comprehensive studies to fully understand potential ecological damage. They argue that the government is moving forward without the necessary safeguards, potentially causing irreversible harm to the marine environment.²¹

The opposition against deep-seabed mining in Norway has been strong from several opposition parties, represented by the Socialist Left Party (SV) and the Green Party (MDG), which criticize forthcoming environmental damages and require more

¹⁹ Deep Seabed Mining: WWF takes legal action against the government. WWF (2024). <https://www.wwf.no/wwf-takes-legal-action-against-the-state-2>

²⁰ *ibid*

²¹ Norway poised to sail past opposition with deep-sea mining licensing plans. Focusingonwildlife (2024). <https://focusingonwildlife.com/news/norway-poised-to-sail-past-opposition-with-deep-sea-mining-licensing-plans/>

profound impact assessments.²² According to them, the decision to proceed with deep seabed mining is driven by economic interests and stands in contrast to environmental protection and sustainability. In particular, the Green Party (MDG) has advocated for an international moratorium on deep-sea mining, as it can be scientifically proven that deep-sea mining is not harmful to biodiversity, important habitats, or natural processes. According to the MDG, Norway should work actively within international fora, especially the International Seabed Authority, to promote such a moratorium.²³

Public opposition to deep-sea bed mining in Norway has manifested in several protests, reflecting growing concerns over the potential environmental impact of the government's decisions. On January 9, 2024, activists gathered outside the Norwegian parliament in Oslo, displaying banners with messages such as

“Stop deep sea mining” and “Norway protect our oceans.” The protest aimed to pressure the government to reconsider its stance on deep-sea mining, highlighting public resistance to the industry's environmental risks.²⁴ Greenpeace Norway has been at the forefront of most of these demonstrations, actively opposing the mining initiative. Greenpeace Campaigner Haldis Tjeldflaat Helle, who was present during the January protest, wished that environmental advocates could stop the industry before it developed. Involvement from Greenpeace and other environmental organizations underlines the wide degree of civil society concern over long-lasting damage to marine ecosystems, and it initiates a strong wave of activism against the industrial exploitation of Norway's seabed.²⁵

In June 2024, the Norwegian Ministry of Petroleum and Energy initiated a three-month public opinion collection period on deep seabed mining, during

²² Deep Seabed Mining: WWF takes legal action against the government. WWF (2024). <https://www.wwf.no/wwf-takes-legal-action-against-the-state-2>

²³ Innstilling fra energi- og miljøkomiteen om Mineralverksemd på norsk kontinentalsokkel – opning av areal og strategi for forvaltning av ressursane. Innst. 162 S (2023–2024). Meld. St. 25 (2022–2023). <https://www.stortinget.no/no/Saker-og-publikasjoner/Publikasjoner/Innstillinger/Stortinget/2023-2024/inns-202324-162s/?all=true>

²⁴ Norway's parliament greenlights controversial deep-sea mining exploration. The local.no (2024). <https://www.thelocal.no/20240109/norways-parliament-greenlights-controversial-deep-sea-mining-exploration>

²⁵ Albert, E.C. (2024). Norway poised to sail past opposition with deep-sea mining licensing plans. <https://news.mongabay.com/2024/10/norway-poised-to-sail-past-opposition-with-deep-sea-mining-licensing-plans/>

which 73 responses were gathered that provided a broad spectrum of perspectives on the proposed areas for seabed mineral exploration. On September 26, 2024, the Norwegian Environment Agency (NEA) submitted a document entitled "Miljødirektoratets kommentarer til arealforslag for utlysning av områder for mineralvirksomhet på havbunnen".²⁶ This submission outlines the agency's perspectives and remarks regarding the proposed initiative to open sections of the Norwegian continental shelf for mineral exploration of the seabed. As one of the most important regulatory bodies responsible for the protection of the environment, NEA is concerned with ensuring that ecological considerations are taken into full account in decisions on resource extraction.

In this submission, NEA raises several critical points. First, they argue that the proposed areas for exploration are too large and call for a more stepwise knowledge-based approach, recommending a reduction in the number of exploration blocks. They expressed concern over the lack of initial environmental assessments and

emphasized the need for rigorous evaluation of potential ecological impacts. Of particular concern is the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, a designated Particularly Valuable and Vulnerable Area (SVO). The NEA recommends excluding overlapping blocks from exploration to protect this fragile ecosystem.

Additionally, NEA urges the exclusion of areas with active hydrothermal vent structures, which are sensitive ecosystems, from potential mining activities. They advocate the development of a comprehensive plan for acquiring environmental data, assigning clear roles and responsibilities to stakeholders, and ensuring stricter regulations for environmental impact assessments and monitoring during the exploration phase. The key theme in NEA's recommendations is the need for a precautionary, adaptive management approach. They contend for legal mechanisms that will enable modification or withdrawal of mining permits in the case of new information about environmental risks. According to NEA, there is a need for a "stopping point" after exploration but before extraction, enabling

²⁶ Miljødirektoratet (2024). Miljødirektoratets kommentarer til arealforslag for utlysning av områder for mineralvirksomhet på havbunnen.

<https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/a7cb434e08e749bcbeb80c5ee3a333ce/miljodirektoratet.pdf?uid=Milj%C3%B8direktoratet#:~:text=juni%202024%20med%20forslag%20til,f%C3%B8rste%20konsesjonsrunden%20innenfor%20%C3%A5pnet%20omr%C3%A5de>.

Careful environmental impact assessments before further actions. They also call for greater transparency, coordination among agencies, and a dynamic plan that would couple resource extraction with marine conservation objectives.

Considering the responses provided by both the business and environmental stakeholders, there is clearly a well-marked division of opinions. Business sees Arctic deep seabed mining as a path for larger economic and technological opportunities, enabling green transition. Proponents of deep seabed mining argue that exploration will encourage data collection, industry growth, and longer-term economic benefits in job creation, and consequently increase the management of marine resources. They also expressed confidence in the ability of technology to minimize environmental risks and appealed for open data sharing to enhance collaboration and increase the pace of research.

Contrary to business views, the scientific community remains highly sceptical. Researchers have raised concerns about the risks and uncertainties of deep-sea mining, emphasizing how it can lead to irreversible damage to marine ecosystems. Following NEA's lead, researchers and NGOs have called for the implementation

of a far more cautious approach given the many environmental impacts associated with opening large areas to exploration. Overall, businesses look toward economic potential and rely on technology to control risks, while researchers emphasize the need for further understanding and caution when protecting marine resources.

Legal implications

Norway's plan to open the Arctic Ocean floor for deep-sea mining exploration is prone to legal challenges. In the stated plan, the proposed deep seabed exploration in the Arctic by Norway is primarily within its continental shelf and extended continental shelf. This means that while Norway has sovereign rights over the seabed in these areas, the water column above the extended continental shelf is considered high seas, so this could potentially contradict the goals of Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ), or the Treaty of the High Seas.²⁷ On the international level, the application of treaties may be disputed, such as UNCLOS and High Seas Treaty, in case the mines would be beyond national jurisdiction. These treaties regulate the usage of ocean floors, and any perceived infraction may generate diplomatic disputes or international legal action.

²⁷ EU (2024). Verbatim report of proceedings. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/CRE-9-2024-01-17-ITM-012_EN.html

Other potential legal hurdles include environmental impact assessments. Several critics have argued that Norwegian assessments lacked a full-scale consideration of the ecological perils from deep-sea mining. If the courts rule that such an assessment failed to meet the standards required by law, further exploration or mining will be held up or blocked.²⁸ Norway's plans can be potentially challenged and complicated by the Svalbard Treaty, which grants equal access to the region's resources to signatory countries. The debate remains undecided on whether the Svalbard Treaty extends to the resources of the seabed, and any overlap between the mining zones and areas protected by the treaty could provoke international legal challenges.²⁹

Other relevant regional agreements include the OSPAR Convention³⁰, protecting the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic. While the convention does not cover mining activities on the Norwegian continental shelf, any potential

harm such as sediment plumes or damage to marine biodiversity could be legally contested or opposed by other states. However, so far, there has not been any official statement from the OSPAR Commission.

Domestically, WWF-Norway is already preparing lawsuits on the basis that the government has failed to consider the risks associated with deep-sea mining. The cases brought to court will probably delay, if not completely block, Norway's deep-sea mining plans and make the government reconsider its strategy in light of both international commitments and environmental protection standards. This field is fast-changing and depends on government decisions and public sentiment towards deep seabed mining; there is an obvious clash in opinion between different stakeholders within Norway. Further research should examine Norway's plans in an international legal context.

²⁸ Gilbert, N. (2024). First approval for controversial sea-bed mining worries scientists. <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-024-00088-7>

²⁹ Perl, A. (2024). Mining the depths: Norway's deep-sea exploitation could put it in environmental and legal murky waters. <https://theconversation.com/mining-the-depths-norways-deep-sea-exploitation-could-put-it-in-environmental-and-legal-murky-waters-220909>

³⁰ OSPAR Convention (1992). <https://water.europa.eu/marine/countries-and-regional-seas/regional-conventions/ospar-convention>